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Interdisciplinary Training Webinar (release 1) D3.5

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the *Cryomicroscopy for macromolecular structure determination* webinar - the first in the planned series of 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars for the Q-SORT project.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars are part of Work Package 3 **Theory, optical testing, and TEM implementation of generalised Sorter** [Months: 1-41], Task 3.5 - Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (M6, M11, M12, M18, M24, M26, M30, M36, M41).

The present document is comprised of 4 Chapters, including Introduction and Conclusions.

The Introduction describes what a webinar is.

Chapter 2 summarises what we mean by Interdisciplinary Training Webinars and what their function is within Q-SORT.

Chapter 3 illustrates context, aims, and content of the first Interdisciplinary Training Webinar of Q-SORT.

The conclusions outline future plans for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHAT IS A WEBINAR?

A webinar is a web-based seminar which can be streamed either live or on demand. It might be just a simple audio stream, or it might include visual aids, such as PowerPoint slides, recorded video clips, or live software demonstrations.

The experience of a webinar attempts to reproduce the benefits of attending a seminar. Audience members can ask questions and the speaker can survey or poll the audience and get feedback as he or she delivers the information.

Webinar technology providers need to support these interactive elements in addition to the basic delivery of the audio and video streams. Keyboard chat features and Q&A are usually subject to more control, whereby the presenters can see messages from the audience and choose whether to broadcast them to all participants, ignore them, or reply privately.

The Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars make use of Vimeo as a platform for playback and of Facebook Live as a platform for live streaming. We chose these platforms as they provide the best value for money and offer the added advantage of being very widespread. On both platforms, users are able to pose questions by posting comments below the video. Answers can be provided by specialists during or after the webinar.

2 THE Q-SORT INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINARS

The Q-SORT project is intrinsically interdisciplinary, being born from the cross-fertilisation of three subjects: light optics (UG, MPI), electron microscopy (CNR, FZJ, UMR, FEI), and biology (MU).

The silo-breaking nature of Q-SORT provides added value through the following cross-fertilisation dynamics: microscopists borrow techniques from light optics specialists and explain back the challenges of the new measurements; biologists explain to physicists the problems that usually arise when studying proteins and suggest alternative proteins for investigation; physicists develop the quantum mechanical approach for cryo-TEM; biologists communicate a priori knowledge to light optics theoreticians in order to streamline efforts in the project work-packages (WP3-WP5).

In order to facilitate mutual learning between physicists and biologists, as well as to foster possible further applications to biology and the life sciences, 9 Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinars have been planned during the lifetime of the project. Their main aim is to function as aids to facilitate the highly interdisciplinary work in WP3 and in the other research WPs. They will do so by providing opportunities for training and mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, for forging a common language, for exchanging ideas for further joint research.

However important their role within Q-SORT, these seminars are meant for everyone, hence the choice to propose them as webinars, so as to reach as wide an audience as possible.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars introduce a sort of 'intermediate level' in the communication of science: i.e. their nature is intermediate between the specialist-to-specialist character of discipline-specific colloquia, talks, and articles and the broad appeal of conventional public understanding of science.

This is why, besides their facilitating function within WP3 and the other research WPs, the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process. Together with the Website, they ensure that Q-SORT will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

In the following paragraph we describe the first of the 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars planned for Q-SORT.

3 THE Q-SORT FIRST INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR:

CRYOMICROSCOPY FOR MACROMOLECULAR STRUCTURE DETERMINATION

The *Cryomicroscopy for macromolecular structure determination* Interdisciplinary Training Webinar was recorded during the second day of the Q-SORT Kick-off Meeting, which was held in Modena on October 02-03, 2017 with the support of CNR NANO (<http://www.nano.cnr.it/index.php?mod=men&id=292>).

This first webinar, which took place before any social media platform was activated, was webcast live via Skype to interested parties - namely the members of the Q-SORT consortium who weren't able to join the seminar in person. The webinar was recorded with two cameras, then edited and mastered for successive on-demand viewing.

The content of the Webinar was agreed upon by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Vincenzo Grillo (CNR) with Prof. Peter Peters (University of Maastricht) and Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED).

Being at the very beginning of the Project, this first webinar was conceived mainly in order to introduce the other Q-SORT partners (mostly physicists) to the applications of cryomicroscopy to the study of biological systems. It has thus been tailor made to be watched on demand: interested parties can re-play it at their convenience by clicking on the following password-protected link:

<https://vimeo.com/262658776>

The password is

Q-SORT_Webinar1

This was the first in a series of interdisciplinary workshops/webinars aimed at promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities. These provide an opportunity for mutual learning and fruitful 'cross pollination' between groups.

3.1 DESCRIPTION

The webinar covers the following topics:

- cryomicroscopy sample preparation
- cryomicroscopy imaging
- dose problems

It aims to prime the transfer of knowledge from biochemists specialised in cryomicroscopy to the physicists community at large.

The aim of the webinar is to provide to other scientists an introduction to the applications of cryomicroscopy to the study of biological systems, highlighting systems of interest and problems that might be addressed by improving physical techniques. Users are able to pose questions by commenting in the Comments section of the video. User questions will be answered by cryomicroscopy specialists.

The experience in Modena was successful and followed by a very active Q&A.

Figure 1 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 1

Figure 2 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 1

4 CONCLUSIONS

This is the first Interdisciplinary Training Webinar produced by Q-SORT.

In the past few years we have seen a consistent rise in the popularity and value of webinars as an essential training, communication, and engagement tool.

The video of the webinar also offers a unique opportunity for engagement. The project will continue to promote on-demand webinars so that their audiences will get larger and more engaged, and spend more time watching webinars, both live and on-demand. In planning the next webinars we will evaluate the effectiveness of this first one and use it as a guideline to help the Q-SORT consortium creating, promoting, and delivering even more successful webinars.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL